

Enki and Ninḥursaĝa

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Entry tags: Ancient Western Asia, Divine powers, Divine functions, Mesopotamian Religions, Ancient Western Asia, Religious Group, Language Isolates, Cosmic domains, Text, Sumerian Text, Ancient Mesopotamian Text, Language, Excavated text, Sumerian

“Enki and Ninḥursaĝa” is a Sumerian literary composition of circa 280 lines that addresses the divine creative processes, at several levels, while exploring the tension between the protagonist deities. Because it is set on a land idyllically described, Dilmun, it was initially compared with the biblical paradise, a notion now long abandoned. Kramer was the first to attempt a full philological publication (1945) whose translation he revised some years later (1955). Attinger presented his own proposal several decades later (1984), followed by other authors in the years to come (Jacobsen 1987; Bottéro and Kramer 1989, Römer 1993, for instance). Though its origins are older (at least from the Ur III period) the main known copies of this composition are dated to the Old Babylonian period and seem linked with school contexts (Rodin 2014:116). Several references point out to a strong influence of its content in the elaboration of the Sumerian compositions known as “Enlil and Ninlil” and “Enlil and Sud” (Cooper 1989, Vantisphout 1987). The narrative begins with an idyllic description of the land of Dilmun (modern day Bahrein), where Enki and his divine consort, Ninsikila rest (lines 1-28), in what can be seen as a state before the divine creative process begun (Lambert and Tournay 1949:122; Alster 1978:16) Yet, as water is lacking, the goddess asks Enki to make the land fertile, to which he complies, further stressing that Dilmun will be so rich that it will become an emporium (lines 29-49). Next, according with the version of the manuscript from Ur, there is an interpolation (Komoróczy 1977) focused on the richness of the trade carried out in this maritime trading port. Numerous products (mainly precious metals, stones, and woods) and several regions, which were commercial partners of the cities of Sumer, are thus alluded (ls. 49A- 49V). Afterwards, the main narrative resumes, with the description of the creation of the abundant waters, as the sun-god Utu rises, thus turning Dilmun into an emporium, as Enki had previously stated (lines 50-62.). This deity is thus described as being within the marshes, where he ejaculated into Nintur/Ninḥursaĝa, who got pregnant and gave birth to Ninnisig (lines 63-87). Three similar sections are then described: from the marshes, Enki sees a goddess (Ninnisig, Ninkura, Ninimma, respectively) who catches his attention, and, after talking with his divine assistant, Isimud, they sail ashore. A sexual act is performed, the goddess gets pregnant, and gives birth to another goddess, who in turn gets the attention of Enki, who is on the marshes, repeating the events (ls. 88-107; 108-126; 126A-126CC, respectively). Uttu seems to break the cycle. In a rather fragmentary passage, she receives instructions from Nintur/Ninḥursaĝa (lines 127-146) and when the narrative resumes, the meeting with Enki is described in different terms: Uttu asks for gifts, to which Enki’s complies (lines 147-165). With the gifts, he presents himself at Uttu’s door, being welcomed inside her house. It is only then that the sexual act is performed (l. 168-189). Impregnated, Uttu gives birth to 8 plants to which Enki, after tasting them, decrees its fates (lines 190-219). This act seems to infuriate Ninḥursaĝa, who curses him, making him ill, a situation which impels a fox to try to mend things (lines 220-246). After some missing lines, Ninḥursaĝa is described as seating Enki on her vagina, healing 8 of his body parts, by creating a deity from each one: Ab-u from the top of the head; Ninsikila from the hair; Ningiriutud from the nose; Ninkasi from the mouth Nazi for the throat; Azimua, from the arm; Ninti from the ribs, and Ensag from the sides (lines 247-271). The narrative comes to an end with new fates being decreed by Ninḥursaĝa to these deities, and with a praise to Enki (lines 272-281) The multi-nuanced fertile actions of Enki can be read as a way to legitimate his power over Ninḥursaĝa within the pantheon. Yet, as Rodin (2014: 218-220) postulated there was still a need to maintain the imperative presence of both female and male deities in the creative processes, which can explain the active role of Ninḥursaĝa throughout the narrative. This interpretation runs parallel to a political-religious discourse of dominance over Dilmun, probably during the Ur III period (Alster 1983:59), which can lead to

other fruitful analyses on the dynamics of ancient southern Mesopotamian context, independent from the (initial) biblical lens.

Date Range: 1900 BCE - 1600 BCE

Region: Mesopotamia2

Region tags: Middle East, Mesopotamia

Mesopotamia

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Rodin, Therese. *The World of the Sumerian Mother Goddess: An Interpretation of Her Myths*. Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis: Historia Religionum 35. Uppsala: Uppsala University, 2014.
- Source 2: Alster, Bendt. 1978. "Enki and Ninhursag: The Creation of the first Woman". UF 10, 15-27.
- Source 3: Cooper, J. R. (1989). Enki's Member: Eros and Irrigation in Sumerian Literature. In: H. Behrens, D. T. Loding and M. T. Roth (eds.), DUMU-E2-DUB-BA-A. *Studies in Honor of Åke W. Sjöberg*. Occasional Publications of the Samuel Noah Kramer Fund, vol. 11, pp. 87-89. Philadelphia: University Museum.

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/cgi-bin/etcsl.cgi?text=t.1.1.1#>
- Source 1 Description: ETCSL translation (and transliteration) of Enki and Ninḫursaĝa (1.1.1)
- Source 2 URL: <https://cdli.mpiwg-berlin.mpg.de/search?simple-value%5B%5D=Enki+and+Nin&simple-field%5B%5D=keyword>
- Source 2 Description: CDLI Literary 000332 (Enki and Ninhursaga) composite (P469514)

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

– Incised or Inscribed

Method of inscription

– Other [specify]: Stylus

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Clay

↳ Clay object
– Clay tablet

↳ Type of clay
– Type of clay: I don't know

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

– Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

Notes: The manuscripts and copies were probably part of several ancient archives/libraries' collections.

↳ Tomb
– I don't know

↳ Cemetery
– I don't know

↳ Temple
– Yes
Notes: probably in its archive/library

↳ Shrine
– I don't know

↳ Altar
– I don't know

- ↳ Devotional marker
 - I don't know
- ↳ Cenotaph
 - I don't know
- ↳ Church
 - No
- ↳ Mosque
 - No
- ↳ Synagogue
 - No
- ↳ Triumphal Arch
 - No
- ↳ Monument
 - No
- ↳ Mass Gathering Point
 - I don't know
- ↳ Cave(s)
 - I don't know
- ↳ Hilltops
 - I don't know
- ↳ Other natural sanctuaries
 - I don't know
- ↳ Boundary markers or lines
 - I don't know

↳ Domestic contexts
– I don't know

↳ Library/archive
– Yes

↳ Specify
– Specify: N/A

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are no data that allow us to speak of a definite religious canon ("official religious scripture") for the religious system of ancient Mesopotamia.

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– I don't know

Notes: As far as I know, it was not used in any specific ritual. However, religious ritual practices in ancient Mesopotamia were not always specified in written/iconographic data.

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

– Yes

↳ Age of extant version of text?

– Yes

↳ Content of text?

– Yes

↳ Ritual purpose of text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There are other Sumerian compositions about Enki's relationship with other goddesses (such as Enki and Ninmah) which are often analysed together by modern scholars, such as Rodin (2014), for example, as well as compositions that seem influenced by this one, such as "Enlil and Ninlil" and "Enlil and Sud" (on the matter, see Cooper 1989 and Vantiphout 1987). However, it's not clear whether they were intended as a collection, in the modern sense of the term

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Notes: On the divine creative power

↳ Behavioral literature?

– Yes

Notes: On what is considered proper sexual advances within the pre-marital sphere; as well as sexual relationships within members of the same (divine) family

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– Yes

↳ Does the lineage involve establish a chain of authority?

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the older goddesses have more authority than the younger ones. This is visible when Ninḫursaĝa/Nintur, the older one, advises Uttu, the last goddess to be born (lines

127-146).

Is the lineage defined by concrete cycles or measures of time?

– Yes

Notes: Each goddess who becomes pregnant gives birth 9 days later, each day compared with a humanly month

How is the lineage established?

–Other [specify]: Family ties. Each new goddess is born from another goddess.

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– I don't know

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

Notes: Enki's sexual behaviour can be seen as reprehensible and aggressive.

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: Ingenious

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– Yes

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– Yes

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– Yes

Notes: Probably, since Enki is the god of wisdom.

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– Yes

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: Though this is a complex matter for the Mesopotamian religious system, as humans can deviate from the divine decrees.

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Can reward

– Yes

↳ Can punish

– Yes

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– Yes

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– Yes

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– Yes

Notes: Enki eats the 8 plants that grew from Uttu.

↳ Can be hurt?

– Yes

Notes: Enki gets ill after eating the 8 plants that grew from Uttu.

↳ Can be tricked?

– Yes

Notes: Though not in this composition, in Inana and Enki, the goddess tricks him to get the divine "me", recurring to her beauty and sensuality, as well as to the effects of the beer and wine he drank.

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: Creative powers; decreeing destinies; intensive sexual potency; aquatic fertility

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– No

Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– No

Notes: Not in this composition

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– Yes

Notes: But not clearly in this composition. I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki.

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– Yes

Notes: But not clearly in this composition. I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– No

Notes: I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki.

- ↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No
Notes: I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki.
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– Yes
Notes: I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki.
Together, the divine assembly knows everything from the cosmic domains, though it is not clearly stated in this composition.
- ↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region
– Yes
Notes: I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki. Several regions outside the Mesopotamian one are mentioned in the composition. Together, the divine assembly knows everything from the cosmic domains.
- ↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– Yes
Notes: I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki.
Together, the divine assembly can see everything humans do, though it is not clearly stated in this composition.
- ↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– Yes
Notes: I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki.
Together, the divine assembly can see everything humans do, though it is not clearly stated in this composition.
- ↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– Yes
Notes: I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki.
Together, the divine assembly can see everything humans do, though it is not clearly stated in this composition.
- ↳ Know basic character (personal essence)
– Yes
Notes: I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki.
Together, the divine assembly can see everything humans do, though it is not clearly stated in this composition.
- ↳ Know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– Yes

Notes: am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki. Together, the divine assembly decrees fates to humans, so in that sense they all know the future. Yet, humans can deviate from those decrees.

↳ Have other knowledge of this world

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings can reward

– Yes

Notes: I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki.

↳ Supernatural beings can punish

– Yes

Notes: I am assuming all the deities depicted in the composition, besides Enki.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– Yes

Notes: The gifts Uttu asks Enki include vegetables and fruits.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: Ninḫursaĝa is enraged with Enki; but is also depicted as wise, when advising Uttu. The goddesses get pregnant, but their pregnancy only lasts 9 days, um day for each human

month.Uttu is depicted as the perfect women;

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes, there are some overlaps and shared power over a specific domain

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

–Specify: Yes. The pantheon was also organized by cosmic functions and roles of deities.

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: a gardener that can be human and a fox.

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: Given that deities decree fates to other deities, it is implicit that their action is monitored by them

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular

– No

↳ Do expectations of ritual offerings play a role in supernatural monitoring?

– No

↳ Supernatural being care about taboos

– I don't know

Notes: Yet, Rodin (2014: 155-157; 167-169) proposes that Enki's sexual act with his progeny, that is, of incestuous nature, is only accepted when referring to a "natural state", which opposes a "cultural one", where and accordingly with Mesopotamian legal sources, is forbidden.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists

– No

Notes: Not in this composition.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions

– No

Notes: Not in this composition.

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities

– No

Notes: Not in this composition.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex

– Yes

↳ Adultery

– Yes

Notes: One can easily interpret the rage of Ninḫursaġa against Enki due also to his adulterous behaviour.

↳ Incest

– Yes

Notes: Following Rodin (2014: 155-157; 167-169) interpretation that Enki's sexual act with his progeny, that is, of incestuous nature, is only accepted when referring to a "natural state", which opposes a "cultural one", where and accordingly with Mesopotamian legal sources, is forbidden.

↳ Taboo about close blood relations (beyond incest) [e.g. from same clan group, village, settlement, so forth].

– I don't know

↳ Specifies taboo regarding power relations (i.e. defines what constitutes abusive behavior)

– I don't know

↳ Does worship/veneration include sex acts/references?

– No

Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Other sexual practices

– Yes

Notes: One can easily interpret the advice of Ninḫursaĝa to Uttu to protect herself from Enki's sexual advances as to a model of "proper" behaviour regarding pre-marital sex.

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying

– Yes

Notes: Not in this composition.

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths

– Yes

Notes: Not in this composition.

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery

– Yes

Notes: Mesopotamian deities are connected with all kinds of magical practices. Enki is one of the divine beings particularly linked with this sphere.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting
 - I don't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping
 - I don't know
 - Notes: The Mesopotamian legal documentation shows social concerns about it. Though it is not clearly stated, to my knowledge, that it is a shared concern by deities.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes
 - I don't know
 - Notes: The Mesopotamian legal documentation shows social concerns about it. Though it is not clearly stated, to my knowledge, that it is a shared concern by deities.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness
 - Yes
 - Notes: If the economy of the land is well, then deities are better served by their human creatures.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect the maintenance of the place?

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other

– Specify: In the Mesopotamian worldview, deities are in control of every single aspect of the cosmos. So, implicitly, they should care about everything

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done only by high god

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings

– Yes

Notes: Ninḫursaĝa punishes Enki. In similar compositions, like "Enlil and Ninlil" and "Enlil and Sud", Enlil behaviour is also punished by other deities

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means

– Yes

Notes: Enki's illness seems to be provoked not only by the plants he eat, but also by Ninḫursaĝa's reaction

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known?

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence?

– No

↳ Done to enforce group norms?

– Yes

Notes: Yes, if we assume Rodin's (2014:155-157; 167-169) interpretation on the incestuous behaviour of Enki as the motif for his punishments

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness?
– No

↳ Done randomly
– No

↳ Other
– I don't know

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife?
– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime?
– Yes

Notes: In this composition, the punishment is for Enki, a deity. But this emphasises what can happen to humans if they don't comply with (divine and human) norms

↳ Highly emphasized by the religious group?
– No
Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Consists of bad luck?
– No
Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Political failure?
– No
Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Defeat in battle?
– No
Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Crop failure or bad weather?
– No
Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Disaster on journeys?
– No
Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Mild sensory displeasure?
– No
Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Extreme sensory displeasure?
– No
Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Sickness or illness?
– Yes
Notes: Enki's health is threatened

↳ Impaired reproduction?
– No
Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Back luck visited on descendants?
– No
Notes: Not in this composition

↳ Other?
–Specify: Not in this composition

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: The pre-marital sexual behaviour; the violent and aggressive male sexual behaviour; the incestuous relationships

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: The way Uttu is described

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– Yes

Notes: Between Ninḫursaġa and Uttu

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

Notes: Ninḫursaġa is convinced to save Enki, thus forgiving him

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– I don't know

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– Yes

Notes: Between the goddesses, specially between Ninḫursaġa and Uttu, Between Isimud and Enki

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– Yes

Notes: Between the goddesses, specially between Ninḫursaġa and Uttu

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: Isimud's relation with Enki

↳ Cooperation

– Yes

Notes: The fox helping Enki.

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

Notes: Enki's and Ninḫursaġa's actions

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– Yes

Notes: Uttu's description

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– Yes

Notes: Uttu's description

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– Yes

Notes: Enki and also Ninḫursaĝa's actions

↳ Strength (physical)

– Yes

Notes: Enki

↳ Power/status/nobility

– Yes

Notes: Enki and Ninḫursaĝa

↳ Humility/modesty

– I don't know

Notes: the way Uttu is described

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– I don't know

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– Yes

Notes: Uttu when receiving the gifts she ask

↳ Optimism/hope

– I don't know

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– I don't know

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– I don't know

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– I don't know

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– Yes

Notes: Ninḥursaġa's advices

Discernment/intelligence

– Yes

Notes: Ninḥursaġa's advices

Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: On all the goddesses

Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Notes: On the Fox preparation.

Other important virtues

– I don't know

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Notes: Again, on the incest, following Rodin (2014:155-157;167-169)

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– I don't know

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– Yes

↳ Drama?

– Yes

↳ Comedy?

– Yes

↳ Tragedy?

– I don't know

↳ Epic entertainment?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– Yes

Notes: The known copies of this composition were identified in loci related to scholar contexts.

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– I don't know

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

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